

THE FORMATION OF STUDENTS' RESEARCH SKILLS, BASED ON THE IDEAS OF ACTIVITY-BASED AND PRACTICE-ORIENTED LEARNING ON ASTRONOMY

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Abstract. *In this paper we consider a system of tasks for the formation of students' research skills, based on the ideas of activity-based and practice-oriented learning. It has proven its effectiveness in studying students' activities in practical and laboratory classes. The developed and implemented electronic educational resource made the process of developing research skills interesting and diverse. This resource is convenient and can be successfully applied in further training. The presented research results, the developed system of tasks and the methodology for their use can be used by university teachers in the practice of teaching future physics teachers*

Key words: *formation of the leading qualities, research activities, activity-based and practice-oriented learning, skills and abilities*

Аннотация. *В данной работе рассматривается система заданий для формирования исследовательских навыков студентов, основанная на идеях деятельностного и практико-ориентированного обучения. Она доказала свою эффективность при изучении деятельности студентов на практических и лабораторных занятиях. Разработанный и внедренный электронный образовательный ресурс сделал процесс формирования исследовательских навыков интересным и разнообразным. Данный ресурс удобен и может успешно применяться в дальнейшем обучении. Представленные результаты исследования, разработанная система заданий и методика их использования могут быть использованы преподавателями вузов в практике обучения будущих учителей физики*

Ключевые слова: *формирование ведущих качеств, исследовательская деятельность, деятельностное и практико-ориентированное обучение, умения и навыки*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada biz faollik va amaliyotga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim g'oyalari asosida talabalarning tadqiqot ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish bo'yicha vazifalar tizimini ko'rib chiqamiz. Amaliy va laboratoriya mashg'ulotlarida talabalar faoliyatini o'rganishda o'zining samaradorligini isbotladi. Ishlab chiqilgan va joriy etilgan elektron ta'lim resursi tadqiqot ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish jarayonini qiziqarli va rang-barang qildi. Ushbu resurs qulay va keyingi mashg'ulotlarda muvaffaqiyatli qo'llanilishi mumkin. Taqdim etilgan tadqiqot natijalari, ishlab chiqilgan vazifalar tizimi va ulardan foydalanish metodikasi universitet o'qituvchilari tomonidan bo'lajak fizika o'qituvchilarini o'qitish amaliyotida qo'llanilishi mumkin.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Yetakchi fazilatlarni shakllantirish, tadqiqot faoliyati, faoliyatga asoslangan va amaliyotga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim, ko'nikma va ko'nikmalar.*

The educational experiment was conducted in such a way that each student performed the tasks we proposed sequentially. The study was conducted within the framework of studying the topic of the physics of the astronomy. Some of the tasks were performed using independent work. The final diagnostics of the level of formation of the research skills was carried out according to the criteria, by checking the work and personal conversations with the students. The points obtained were recorded. This allowed us to evaluate the level of formation of the research

skills quite fully and objectively. Control was carried out in the following areas: development of research skills; ability to solve different types of problems; ability to perform laboratory work.

It should be noted that the main mission of control is to provide feedback, awareness of the compliance of practical results about the subject studied and the final goals. If the actual results always coincided with the set ones, then control would hardly ever be appropriate [1].

Thus, during the ascertaining experiment it was established that the level of formed research skills is characterized by low indicators. Moreover, the formed skills and abilities are distinguished by a low level of awareness and generalization, which is directly related to durability. This situation is largely due to the presentation of the content of the educational material and the nature of the learning activities of students in the learning process. The results of the ascertaining experiment determined the direction of the search for ways to improve the methodology for forming research skills. This direction consisted in developing a system of tasks and laboratory work on astronomy that meet the requirements of a practice-oriented approach to training and the corresponding stages of forming research skills.

The purpose of the formative experiment was to test the effectiveness of the system of laboratory works we developed and the methodology for their use. The formative experiment was conducted in 2023-2024. It involved students majoring in "Astronomy" and the faculty of the Physics Department. We assumed that the system of tasks and laboratory works we developed, as well as the electronic resource, contribute to more effective development of research skills. This means that these skills are practiced more productively if the teacher purposefully selects and designs tasks and organizes the work itself. At the initial stage of the formative experiment, we determined the initial level of formed research skills (for 3 courses), the data obtained did not differ significantly from the data of the ascertaining experiment. We took them as a basis for subsequent comparison [2].

Table 1 and Figure 1 provide data on the diagnostics of the formed motivational readiness of students for research activities in the process of independent work at the initial stage of the study. The study revealed that at the initial stage, the low level prevailed. The students' interest in research activities was not always stable, many of them were often passive. Students who showed an average level are interested in research activities, but their knowledge of it is incomplete. The number of high-level students is small, these students realize the importance of research activities in their studies and profession.

Table 1- Level of formation of students' motivational readiness for research activities

Level of training	Interest in research activities	Dependence of the application of educational tools on the educational situation	Activity in research activities
	Quantity in %	Quantity in %	Quantity in %
High	8	8	8
Average	22	18	22
Short	70	74	70

In terms of the students' formed knowledge of the theory of research activities at the initial stage of the study, low and medium levels also prevailed. Many students have some theoretical knowledge of research activities, but cannot relate it to their practical activities. The number of students with a high level is also small. These are students who have sufficient knowledge of the theory of research and are ready to apply it.

We also investigated the number of correctly performed actions at the initial stage of the study. In general, the level of students' preparation in terms of their ability to perform laboratory work and solve problems can be considered satisfactory. Students who performed all their academic work according to a model turned out to be at a low level. When mistakes were made, they corrected them when the teacher pointed them out and with his/her active participation. Data on diagnostics of the formed motivational readiness of students for research activities.

Fig. 1- Level of formation of students' motivational readiness for research activities at the initial stage of the study

Table 2- Level of students' formed knowledge on the theory of research activities

Levels of training	Level	Indicators		
		Completeness	Strength	Quality
Age	High	20	20	16
	Average	55	60	57
	Low	25	20	27

Fig 2- Level of students' formed knowledge on the theory of research activities at the initial stage of the study

Students at the intermediate level were able to complete up to 75% of the tasks, but sought help from the teacher. They corrected errors when the teacher pointed them out and provided his/her advisory assistance. A sufficient number of students were able to correctly complete more than 75% of the required tasks. If mistakes were made, they find and correct them independently. However, we noted that the majority of tasks were also completed under standard conditions, without transferring existing knowledge. Diagnostics of the number of correctly performed actions at the initial stage of the study [3].

Table 3- Data on the number of correctly performed actions

Level of training	Indicators		
	Quantity Right completed tasks	Number of correctly completed stages in work	Number of correctly completed laboratory tasks
High	80	72	51
Average	12	14	39
Low	8	14	10

This information made it possible to determine the completeness of the acquired knowledge and methods of activity, as well as the possibility of their transfer to new or changed conditions, when conducting research work and tasks of a productive, creative nature.

Fig. 3- Data on the number of correctly performed actions (n) at the initial stage of the study

As can be seen from the diagrams, the level of formation of the leading qualities of research skills at the final stage of the study is noticeably higher. We have noted that for many students there has been a transition to interest in research activities, many have realized its necessity. The number of students who are active and proactive in conducting research has increased. Many noted a desire to engage in research in their future work. The developed system of tasks (problems and laboratory works) for the formation of students' research skills, based on the ideas of activity-based and practice-oriented learning, has proven its effectiveness in studying students' activities in practical and laboratory classes. Active, conscious assimilation of educational material had a positive effect not only on the formation of research skills, but also on motivation for educational activities in general. The developed and implemented electronic educational resource made the process of developing research skills interesting and diverse. This resource is convenient and can be successfully applied in further training. The presented research results, the developed system of tasks and the methodology for their use can be used by university teachers in the practice of teaching future physics teachers.

Conclusion

The results of the experimental work confirmed that the system of specially designed tasks (by types of research activities) and laboratory work on the physics of the astronomy have a positive effect on the formation of research skills of future physics teachers. The conducted research substantiates the necessity of purposeful formation of research skills as an important and necessary component of professional training of future physics teachers. Research skills not only improve the quality of education at the university, but also provide an effective tool for successful scientific and pedagogical activity. The presence of such skills and involvement in research activities also affects the development of the personality and general culture of the future teacher. It is these specialists who are in demand now in the labor market.

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